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The Paradoxical Problem of Child Marriage in India

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ABSTRACT

Marriage in India is always celebrated with great pomp and splendour in the life of every adult, but there are no such valid reasons for celebration in child marriage. Such marriages are rampant and spread across India. Girls are regarded as liabilities and therefore parents believe them in getting them married at an early age. The major reasons are poverty, backwardness and illiteracy. These conditions deprive the young girls from participating in activities related to childhood. Once married, they are encumbered to perform different chores having little or no knowledge of it. Lack of education takes away their future opportunities of proper employment and overall development. This paper is written with an objective to develop an understanding of the legalities surrounding child marriage and to gain insights on the determinants and consequences of child marriage.

Keywords: Child Marriage, Early Marriage, Legal Measures, Child Abuse

INTRODUCTION

The institution of marriage is a solemn occasion of immense joy and celebration particularly in the Indian society. It is also one of the most important events that encumbers upon almost every social and economic obligation, kinship bonds and traditional norms and values. However, child marriage in the country is still prevalent even though the practice is considered to be against the law. Due to the complex web of socio-economic and cultural factors, poor implementation of laws, etc., child marriage takes place violating the human rights of the adolescent girls. The reasons cited are poverty, no importance to female education, lack of knowledge regarding reproductive and child health, the inability to pay a higher dowry with increasing age, the fear to face society if the girl isn't married and most importantly, the desire to control her sexuality. Such reasons increase the prevalence of child marriage and thus perpetrate violence on the young bride which scars her for her whole life. The child bride becomes vulnerable to different forms of abuses suffering from severe

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bruises and damages since she has to bear the pain of giving birth to children at a very tender age when her body is not physically and mentally fit for motherhood.

The NHFS-4 (2015-2016) data of India reveals that 26.8% of women between the ages of 14-20 years were already victims of child marriage. Moreover 7.9% of women aged between 15-19 years have already attained motherhood or were pregnant when the survey was conducted. In India, child marriage is pervasive in various nooks and corners of the country, where the young girl is married off before she is physically and mentally matured to bear the various tasks of being a wife and a mother. Within the complex structure of societal traditions and customs, economic factors and the deeply rooted prejudices child marriage remains ingrained leaving behind physical and emotional scars for life. The paper based on secondary data tries to look into the hegemonic practice of child marriage in India, the legal provisions and the various determinants and consequences of child marriage.

THE HEGEMONIC PRACTICE OF CHILD MARRIAGE IN INDIA

Child marriage has been a trend in India for decades and centuries. As soon as girls enter into the institution of marriage, they are forced to become women even if they are too young. These young girls endure misery and most of its impact remains hidden.

The case of Rukhmabai was the first case in the 19th century that brought to light the fight against the evil practice of child marriage. Rukhmabai, the first lady doctor to practice medicine in India was herself a child bride who was married off by her mother under societal pressure when she was 11 years of age to a person named Dadaji Bhikaji, who was 19 years of age at that time. Hardly educated and unwilling to develop himself, her husband demanded his conjugal rights when he turned 20 years old which made him file a case in the court for demanding his marital rights over her. The case was compromised on the grounds of Rukhmabai's husband accepting an amount of two thousand rupees as compensation saving Rukhmabai from going to prison (Burton, 1998; Pal, 2016; Bahukhandi, 2017).

The second case was Phulmonee's death, an 11 year old child bride, forcefully married to a man of 35 years. She succumbed to death because of vaginal split by her husband Hari Maiti, who forced himself upon her and left her bleeding to death. According to the Hindu norms, it was accepted that once the child bride attains puberty, sexual intercourse with their wives is considered to be legal. It further stated that there will be penalty of

marital rape only if the child wife is under ten years of age. Hari Maiti therefore was exempted from the charge of rape but was held responsible for the death of Phulmonee unconsciously by a rash or casual act. It was because of Phulmonee's case, the government took the decision to increase the age of consent from 10 years to 12 years for marriage of girls (Sarkar, 2000).

The above two cases give an idea of how men exert control over women physically or psychologically through the institution of marriage they are always expected to offer their consent unconsciously or consciously to their subordination before male power is secured. Arnot(1982) states that women have accepted the patriarchal culture irrespective of the various forms of abuses making themselves subjugated by men throughout their lives. Men having authority frequently dominate women since they are considered inferior to them leading to harassment of the latter. It is a common sight for men to exercise hegemony over women by showing their strength in harassing women mentally, physically and sexually within the institution of marriage thereby making men stronger and women weaker. Thus, women all over the world suffer hegemony and harassment by men because they have accepted that men are the ones who achieve the best of everything and are masterful while women are the one who underachieves and defers. They are always encouraged to choose their inferior status freely and accept their exploitation as natural.

LEGAL PROVISIONS AGAINST CHILD MARRIAGE

The above two cases helped in increasing the age at marriage along with taking into serious consideration the concern of choice and consent within the institution of marriage which further led to discussions and legal formalities with regards to child marriage in the twentieth century.

The bill, known as the Sarda Bill, intended to prevent the solemnisation of child marriage was taken forward in the constituent assembly by Rao Haribilas Sarda on 20th September, 1929. According to the law, a fine of Rs 1000 along with imprisonment up to a month were made legally binding to the adults who were responsible for solemnizing marriages of below fourteen years of age. Moreover, if the groom was found to be below 21 years of age, he could be imprisoned too. However, there were instances where adults who conducted the marriage were of the opinion that married girls were over the legal age since there was no proper documentation in order to prove the actual age making such claims valid (Hatekar, Mathur &

Rege, 2007). Thus, such loopholes within the law continued to favour and perpetuate this evil in society.

The Prohibition of Child Marriage Act, 2006 substituted the Child Marriage Restraint Act, 1929. The shift from the Child Marriage Restraint Act reflects the stronger target of the country not only to restrain solemnization but prohibition of such marriage where the groom has not attained 21 years of age and the bride has not completed 18 years of age. The three purposes of the Act were “prevention of child marriages, protection of children involved and prosecution of offenders.” It prescribes punishment for the ones who solemnize or encourages such marriages. The punishment for a male has been fixed at imprisonment of up to two years or with a fine of one lakh rupee or both and demanding maintenance and habitation for the child bride until her remarriage. Due to limited knowledge regarding the implementation of the laws and the penalty associated with it, prohibition of child marriage is negligible that undermines the functioning of the Act.

Majority of the societies do not oppose child marriage, rather express their unwillingness to deal with the issue. Such case is of Bhanwari Devi hailing from Rajasthan who herself being a child bride campaigned against a child marriage and reported such incidents to the authorities. When she went to stop a marriage of a girl who was nine-months old, she was raped for opposing such a long standing custom. The moment she went public with her complaint, she was charged of lying. Moreover, the police did not take her case sincerely, and the government denied taking strict action against the culprits ignoring the different protests staged by the various groups of women. This case reflects how inactive laws are that safeguard to work for the elimination child marriage. Bhanwari’s case gives us an idea about the various challenges faced by the individuals and the organizations working towards eliminating child marriage in the country (Manchanda, 1996; Gupta, 2012; Murthy, 2013).

Even after the existence of a law that aims to restrain the evil practice of child marriage, it is still a reality in our country making the overall growth of the child crippled. Even today girls in the nooks and corners in the country are socialized to accept child marriage as the norm. Despite the existence of punitive measures society gives more importance in organizing and perpetuating the evil practice. In order to safeguard the interests of children, collective efforts should be taken to reduce child marriage by socially isolating the ones who practices it.

DETERMINANTS OF CHILD MARRIAGE

The major factors that perpetuate early marriages are traditions and customs, poverty, patriarchy, lack of education and the urge for protection of girls from unwanted sexual relationships outside marriage (Srinivasan et al., 2015; UNICEF, 2001). They are discussed in detail below.

Traditions and Customs

In India, majority of the societies regard customs and traditions in high esteem. The possession of traditional perspectives and viewpoints are also regarded as aspects that encourage child marriages. It is believed that early marriage would lead to improvements in the living conditions of young girls.

Kulkarni (1994) is of the opinion that parents who have more than one daughter wish that their daughters be married before the legal age in order to avoid the wedding expenses which proportionately rise with the rise in the girl's age; and also to reduce the fear of their daughters going astray. The occurrence of child marriage leads to different vulnerabilities for child brides which are mostly the outcome of the patriarchal notions such as social constructions of gender, decision making, traditional rituals that are mostly biased towards men in the society and certain superstitious beliefs making woman as a scapegoat. Society thus, prescribes child marriage as a necessity for girls rather than delaying for preserving their chastity (Santhya, Haberl and & Singh, 2006).

Despite the existence of various customs and traditions that encourage the continuation of the social evil, there are economic reasons associated with it too as the drivers of early marriage. Poverty of the families put pressure on them by sending their daughters to the marital family at the earliest since the rate of dowry increases once the girl gets older (Haberl and, Chong & Braken, 2004).

Poverty

The highest prevalence of child marriage is in South Asia (56%) where women between the ages of 20-49 years marry before the legal years of marriage, i.e. 18 years. Globally, one out of three child marriages takes place in India (UNICEF, 2007). According to the 2011 Census, there were roughly 12 million child marriages amongst the girls below 18 years of age and boys below 21 years of age in India.

Girl children are forced to become child brides since they come from poorer households. When resources and opportunities are limited and

societal risks becomes more acute, it forces parents to marry their daughters at the earliest putting them in a disadvantaged position. Lower levels of economic development and child marriage compounded with poverty have a close relation that ends in victimizing the young girls. However, the reasons parents consider to marry their daughters do not secure the lives of their daughters in their marital family. Majority of the families with limited resources feels that the best option to secure their daughters lives is through early marriage since there are no alternatives to child marriage by making them dependent on the husband and the marital family (Parsons et al, 2015; Lemmon, 2014; Pells, 2011; Mathur et al., 2003).

However, the reasons stated earlier do not alone perpetuate the social evil, be it poverty or traditional customs which are mostly the factors influenced by the decision making surrounding marriage. The most important factor is patriarchy which is deeply rooted in the society leading to complex realities resulting in continuation of child marriage.

Subjugation of Women

Child marriage takes place because of the established societal norms in the patriarchal structure which aims to perpetuate the custom. In India, child marriage is deeply rooted due to gender disparity, where young girls are discriminated on the basis of education, employment and sexuality.

Santhya and Jejeebhoy (2007) concur that due to rigid patriarchal structures, the young married women are subjugated by the male stratum of the family where they are particularly vulnerable and unable to exercise any choice in their marital homes. The married adolescents hardly interfere in decisions related to their lives, their mobility and interaction with outsiders. In a patriarchal society, the birth of a son is considered as a feeling of happiness but in case of the birth of a daughter, it is considered to be an occasion for mourning. It is due to the birth of a daughter, the position of a woman accordingly goes down in the society and the household. Majority of the married women are either beaten or ill-treated because of their inability to give birth to a son. Due to the supremacy of the patriarchal system, the lineage is figured along the male line where the property and name passes from the father to the sons and it is always the supervision of the father that is considered to be supreme within the family (Ghosh, 1991).

The role of a girl is limited to that of a daughter, wife and a mother where she is regarded as a possession of her father and husband which is basically the norm of a patriarchal society. Even after setting the legal marriageable age, child marriage takes place forcefully dropping out girls from school.

Lack of Education

Child marriage often means an abrupt end to the education of a girl. Most of the girls usually drop out of school before their marriage because parents find no benefits in educating their daughters as marriage seems to be the ultimate solace for them. Lack of socio-economic opportunities coupled with poverty, security of the girls etc., acts as a barrier in attaining education of the girl child.

According to UNICEF (2007), the phenomenon is highly related to girls being in school within 10-14 years of age. Girls who receive formal education beyond the primary level tend to marry late. Once married, girls are rarely permitted to continue their education. Educational attainment becomes a dream for those who marry early because these young girls leave their natal homes very early and try to cope with the different problems in their new marital life. Besides, knowing the fact that they need to be married off soon, leaves an impression on the parents that there is no point in educating them (Gorney, 2011).

The NHFS-4 (2015-2016) findings reveals that 30.8% of the girls between the age of 15-19 years in India have never been to school and were already married before the legal age during the time of survey while 21.09% attained education till primary level. 10.2% of girls who received secondary education were married too before 18 years of age. Due to the existing gender disparities, the literacy level of women is lesser than men. Young girls are found to continue their education until they reach the stage of menarche. Once they attain puberty, their names are withdrawn from the school because of the fear of misusing their virginity by outsiders resulting in unequal attainment of education for the girls in rural areas making them devoid of skills to have a livelihood of their own (Chakravarty, 1998).

After marriage, they usually have limited opportunities for acquisition of education and getting engaged in employment opportunities. The individuals in their marital homes are meant to make major decisions in terms of their lives, more so in case of education and employment. When girls are not enrolled in schools and there is lack of education among them, they succumb to the perils of early marriage, which proves to be disadvantageous to them to a major extent.

Virginity of a Girl Child

Parents prefer marrying their daughters at an adolescent age in order to prevent themselves from unwanted social humiliation since family honour

and preference for virgin are given a high social value. The chastity of a girl is of utmost importance in the patriarchal society of India.

Marriage is regarded as a medium to keep the girl away from unsafe sexual relations and protect the honour of the family, and that young girls are easy to control and hence they are preferred. Virginity of a girl is regarded as a prized possession before her marriage in order to avoid illegal sexual activity. The existing society acts a shield over the personal choices of the women when it comes to expressing their sexuality, pain and danger which also results in the violation of their human rights (Mohlakoana, 2008; Kapadia, 1966).

The above cited points are only a few of the reasons among the multiple reasons that lead to increasing number of child marriages. The patriarchal society together with poverty, deeply rooted customs, and inability to attain education make the young girls suffer the most resulting in serious and lifelong effects on the emotional, physical and psychological well-being of the child brides. These consequences of child marriage are disturbing and often determine where life leads to, thereby making the child brides live in poverty leading to negligible access to service and privileges in the society.

CONSEQUENCES OF CHILD MARRIAGE

Young girls desire to study, learn and get involved in various tasks and activities that render a significant contribution in enriching their lives. Girls tend to suffer severely than boys because of the aftermath of child marriage. In rural areas, girls are trained in terms of implementation of household responsibilities rather than taking pleasure in learning and enjoying their childhood. Child marriage deprives them from taking pleasure in childhood activities, exercising their choice about their sexual and reproductive health leading to violation of human rights which are discussed below.

Childhood at Loss

Childhood is one of the important phases in the life of every individual that impacts overall healthy growth and development. However, it is considered to be one of the most difficult periods for young girls as they succumb to the perils of early marriage. Early marriage tends to shorten a girl's childhood resulting in stopping her education and impacting her health (Nour, 2009; Wodon, 2016). Through child marriage, the aspirations and childhood of the girls are crushed making them devoid of their basic human rights, depriving them of educational opportunities, freedom of choice,

decision making and financial independence that could have accompanied them as a result of education and self-empowerment. Girls tend to shatter their childhood once they are burdened with domestic chores which is followed by child marriage without understanding the true meaning neither of marriage nor of family life.

Kundu et al. (2007) speak about the time of transition from childhood into adulthood which is lost when girls forced into early marriage in Indian context. Child marriage denies girls the right to health often pressurizing them to jumpstart into the world of motherhood. They are most likely to experience various forms of violence all the way through their lives bringing an abrupt end to their childhood. Such experiences are worsened by the incomprehensibility of marital and sexual life and tend to leave deep traumas and a longing for the joys of childhood which is snatched from them.

Impact on Reproductive and Child Health

The reproductive health of a woman is a vital and crucial component in her lifetime. Most of the young brides have inadequate knowledge regarding access to contraception and reproductive health care services. Before the girls become physically mature and psychologically ready, they fall prey to unsafe sexual practices and unwanted pregnancy making them susceptible to the various risks associated with it. In their marital homes, no one pays adequate attention towards health care needs of the child brides. Even when they are not feeling well or experience health problems or illnesses, then too, they are compelled to get involved in carrying out the household responsibilities.

Santhya and Jejeebhoy (2007) reveal that young women come across many obstructions in matters related to sexual - reproductive health decisions (unwanted pregnancy) and other associated choices related to their lives. The young brides are obliged to prove their ability to give birth prematurely making them susceptible to various frightful injury and sickness while delivering a child putting them and their children at a danger of dying.

According to UNICEF (2007), a girl under the age of 15 years is five times more likely to die during premature pregnancy and childbirth than a woman in her twenties. The risks associated with pregnancy extends to the infants too. Many a times, these young women are prone to complications during child birth. The new mother being a child herself faces a lot of difficulties in mothering her own children since they are not physically capable of bearing children. Young mothers who are forced to take the role of a

married woman and a mother experience higher rates of maternal mortality.+

While the Maternal Mortality Rate according to the Sample Registration System (SRS) data released by the Registrar General of India was 130 deaths per 1,00,000 live births (Arokiasamy & Yadav, 2014). While the Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) according to the NHFS-4 (2015-2016) was 41 deaths per 1000 live births. 59 deaths per 1000 live births amongst the mothers whose age at birth was less than 20 years were reported from the survey.

The child brides are expected to perform the household tasks in their marital home along with childbearing and childcare. The phenomenon is not as widespread among boys because of the physical dangers associated in relation to girls in case of early childbirth, or status and power in the household is rampant.

Sexually Disadvantaged Position of the Child Bride

Young girls and child brides have limited mobility in the society, and the adolescent phase becomes a silent phase since their voices are not heard. The patriarchal society looks forward to marrying girls as children in order to prevent them from having illicit affair outside marriage. Virginity, virtue and purity are the factors that personify her, the honour of the family, community and a nation that clings onto her sexuality and womanhood.

The husband has right to sex and has sole control over fertility issues in the post marriage scenario making the young women subjected to injustices that are deeply rooted which regards women as sex objects resulting in detrimental consequences on her health, early sexual life and unwanted pregnancies. Women in India are characterized as Goddesses with immense powers; where she is worshipped, but the harsh reality is that she is controlled by regulating her sexuality (Daskoch, 2013; George, 2002). Ouattara, Sen and Thomson (1998) unveil a picture of forced early sexual experiences which brings to light the sexual helplessness of the newly married women. Lack of awareness and prevalent misconceptions among young women make them fall prey to forceful sex by their husbands. Sexual violence within the institution of marriage is very relevant that has a range of problems. Frequent sexual activity and subsequent reproduction makes her maintain a good bonding with her spouse, else she will be treated violently if she fails to listen to demands of her husband resulting in various forms of violence.

Violence and Abandonment

The United Nations Declaration on the Elimination of Violence against Women (1993) defines violence against women as, “any act of gender-based violence that results in, or is likely to result in, physical, sexual or psychological harm or suffering to women, including threats of such acts, coercion or arbitrary deprivation of liberty, whether occurring in public or in private life”. Violence includes physical, sexual, verbal, mental, emotional and economic abuse.

The NHFS-4 survey of India (2015-2016) revealed that 33% of women in the age group of 15- 49 years have experienced violence. According to The National Crime Records Bureau data (2016) shows that the rate of crime against women per 1,00,000 female population was 55.2 % where the most reported crime against women was “cruelty by husbands or his relatives”, accounted to 33% of all crimes.

According to Krishnaraj (2007) marriage thrust various responsibilities of adulthood on young girls and invites violence for non-performance or neglect of expected behaviour. The child brides in their marital family are devoid of having a say in any events surrounding their lives. They end up deserting their desires and ambitions, and succumb to the dangers of teenage pregnancy and other forms of physical and emotional violence. Women tend to accept that it is right for the husbands to beat them which highlight the role of social mores and their effect on social perception. The various forms of oppression can only be understood from the viewpoint and experiences of the subjugated women only when they speak of their experiences (Kopelman, 2016; Jenson and Thornton, 2003).

Violation of Human Rights

The rights of the girl children are violated once they fall into the trap of child marriage curtailing their overall development. Women in India are still considered to be backward and marginal in all spheres of life where they are neglected by the policy makers, administrators and the ruling class. Almost in all spheres of life, men dominate the different socio-economic activities of women which in turn put them in a detrimental position regardless of the various laws available that aims to safeguard to position of women and protect their human rights.

The Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) regards child marriage as “a human rights violation and a harmful practice that disproportionately affects women and girls globally, preventing them from living their lives free from all forms of violence”.

Human rights of women are violated in child marriage where women experience infringement with regards to forceful marriage without taking their consent. The rights of the young women are denied within the institution of marriage which is considered to be the most private sphere of the life of an individual (Ouattara, Sen and Thomson ,1998).

Violation of the rights of the young women leads to consequences that are grave for them, in relation to their health, social status, domestic violence and deprivation of land and property where they lack in ability to determine their own lives. Irrespective of the various rights attributed to them, women are still not aware of the rights because they are used to acceptance of such treatment without any hesitation. The situation of human rights with regards to women in India is miserable where often Indian women are looked at in terms of violation, humiliation and crimes against women both at the state, societal, familial and individual level.

CONCLUSION

As a result of prevalence of the above stated determinants, the practice of child marriage still exists. The major consequences of child marriage primarily have an unfavourable influence upon girl children. Poverty which is certainly one of the issues but regressive societal and cultural norms, patriarchy, lack of education and protection of the girl child because of their sexuality are some of the key factors behind the occurrence of child marriage that snatches away their future compelling them to stay in environment they are unprepared for. Child marriages continue to abuse young girls by struggling poverty and placing too much emphasis on the purity of women while patriarchal values are heavily ingrained. Hence, it can be stated that child marriage imposes barriers within the course of leading to improvement within their overall quality of life.

The complexity of child marriage is an outcome of the above mentioned factors along with the ingrained patriarchal norms making the future of the child brides' grave which therefore needs attention. For the prevention of child marriage, it is very important for the individuals belonging to rural communities, and deprived and socio-economically backward sections of the society to understand that girls should be made provision of equal opportunities as boys. In addition to educational opportunities, they work towards enhancement of their skills and abilities, maintain effective terms and relationships with them and do not consider them as liabilities. When positive viewpoints are formed in terms of girl children, then progress opportunities would be made available to them, preventing child marriages.

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